

Management Graduate's and Their Suitability to the Corporate Sector

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: May

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3335428>

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Introduction to Higher Education

This Chapter is an introduction to Indian Higher Education System and in particular the present Management Program. This chapter also includes information about the present Corporate Scenario and the suitability of existing Management Curriculum to meet the Corporate Expectations. Countries like India need to assess the relevancy of Academic Output from Higher Academic Institutions as per the changes in Global economic environment.

The review of literature illustrates every year approx 9 million graduates are being produced by the academic institutions from various streams and most of them are being absorbed by the Industries at various cadres to channelize the turn of our economy. These Recent College Graduates (RGS) are provided basic training to tune up with the Industrial climate. It is rightly said, "What is really needed to make Democracy function is not knowledge of facts but right Education"- Mahatma Gandhi.

Research Scholar

"Higher Education contributes to the promotion of Civic behaviours, Nation-building and Social cohesion through the transmission of democratic values and cultural norms. This supports the formation and strengthening of social capital, generally understood as the benefit of membership in a social network that can provide access to resources, guarantee accountability and serve as a safety net in times of crisis. The institutions, relationships and norms that emerge from Higher Education are instrumental in influencing the quality of society's interactions, which underpin economic, political and social development. Higher Education Institutions are at the crossroads for social co-operation, which can foster strong networks, stimulate voluntary activity and promote extracurricular learning and innovation." - V.N. Rajasekaran Pillai, Vice-chairman, UGC.

The famous philosopher Einstein while discussing the need for education has projected the following fundamentals:

- To educate the individual as a free individual: To understand and use critical thinking skills,

- To educate the individual as a part of society: Virtually all our knowledge, our clothes, our food is produced by others in our society, thus, we owe society and have responsibility to contribute back to society,
- Through education, knowledge must continually be renewed by ceaseless effort, if it is not to be lost. It resembles a statue of marble which stands in the desert and is continually threatened with burial by the shifting sand. The hands of service must ever be at work, in order that the marble continue to lastingly shine in the sun.

According to Ronald Barnett (1992), there are Four Predominant Concepts of Higher Education

1. Higher Education as the production of Qualified Human Resources,
2. Higher education as Training for a Research Career,
3. Higher education as the efficient Management of teaching provision,
4. Higher education as a matter of extending Life chances.

Higher Education is generally understood as to cover teaching, research and extension. But, in real, if we analyse each concept of Higher Education, the Higher Education plays a different role in the society. The 21st century is emerging with new society, where knowledge is the primary resource of production instead of capital. Efficient utilization of this existing knowledge can create comprehensive wealth for the Nation and improve the quality of life-in the form of good communication facilities, quality education, better infrastructure, science and technology, health care facilities, and other social indicators.

1. To prepare students for research and teaching,
2. To provide highly specified training course adopted to the needs of economic and social life,
3. To be open to all, so as to cater to the many aspects of life long education,
4. To promote international co-operation through Internationalization of Research, technology networking and free movement of persons and scientific ideas (UNESCO-1996).

Since the achievement of Independence, the Indian Government aim is to provide education and equalizing educational opportunities to all. Accordingly, the Higher Educational Institutions have been visualized with an aim of advancing quality education to develop a compliant citizen, who has a clear idea about his roles and responsibilities in the society, and focuses on the interrelationship of quality education and quality of life. But to achieve this, all important instruments and the agencies contributing to or responsible for, this growth should be integrated in order to ensure all round development.

The Public Universities, in general, plays a major role in regulating the Academic activities on their campuses as well as their areas of jurisdiction through the affiliating system. Even the private institutions enjoyed large- scale financial support in the form of grants. Private funds as well as individuals played key roles in the cause of higher education.

Ministry of Human Resources Development (MHRD) reveals that there has been an increasing awareness among the people of our, that the Country should be looked upon as it's valuable resource-indeed and that our growth process should be based on the Integrated Development of the Citizen, beginning with childhood and going right through life.

In pursuance of this idea, a new Ministry was created under a suggestive name, Ministry of HRD on 26th Sept, 1985, through 174th amendment to the Government of India (allocation of business) Rules 1961.

Currently the Ministry has two Departments Namely

1. Department of School Education and Literacy, and
2. Department of Higher Education.

In terms of number of students, Indian higher education and research sector is the largest in the World. Very few Universities in India have made their way in the recent internal ranking. Of the top 200 Universities of the World, except the IIT Kanpur ranked at 29, University of Delhi at 130, IIT Chennai ranked at 132 1.

But the review of literature gives a broad picture that, recently, the number of Private Institutes in the country has increased impressively where as the number of Public Institutions and Aided Institutions has increased only marginally. Though the count of Educational Institutes increasing in the country the quality output of students are compromised every year. When we are looking for a quality life through quality education, we should have a broader vision of education. The short-term market-oriented focus of educational programs, the unstable and unbalanced emphasis on offering of only job-oriented programs by the educational institutions is a result of a narrow view and lack of preparation of the purpose and goals of education.

Management Education in India

As a concept, the management education was first developed in USA, in 1881 (with the funding of Joseph Wharton) Wharton School of Finance and Economy at the University of Pennsylvania (Pierson 1959). This program was seen as significant to be referred as MBA program as idealistic business education. Then in 1906, the first well-known full-fledged Management School was established by Harvard University inspired by Wharton School, was the notion of professionalism. Until a few decades ago, however, the Management Education has not gained prominence. MBAs had over the years gone through roadblocks in terms of acceptance, visibility and credibility in the eyes of the Corporate World (Vijayasathy 2004).

The emergence of professionalism and significant increase in the demand for Management Graduates in the Corporate Sector paved way to rise the status of MBA program, and is closely linked to the Globalization, competitive global business environment and its increasing importance. The demand from the employment market has in turn led to a significant expansion of Management Education across the world. This is evidenced by the spurt in the number of business schools from both the private and public sectors. Today, from a wealth-creating economy point of view, the challenge of Management Education is to develop new skills, including 'Employability' skills and the expertise needed to undertake 'knowledge work'. Investment in knowledge and skills brings direct economic returns to individuals and society (Scottish Executive 2005). People who gain knowledge, skills and competencies through learning will invariably contribute to the economic development of Nations. Management education thus plays a vital role in enhancing competitiveness in a global knowledge society.

Management Education in the country can roughly be divided into Four Groups

- The First group is at the top, and are the reputed institutes like
- IIM, IIT. etc., imparting high quality of education.
- The Second category is those institutes, started by industrial houses, which offer some surety of a job after the course.
- The Third category is the university departments which have not been able to impart quality education but can provide jobs in regional industrial groups.
- The Fourth category is those institutes which have neither the advantage of low fees of a university nor the backing of an industrial house.

Recently, a number of academicians, retired people, politicians and others have started such institutes which remain essentially money making devices.

Areas in Management Education

Marketing, Finance, Production and Personnel are the four major areas in management with each having several sub-branches.

- **Marketing Management:** Includes sales, purchase, domestic and international marketing (exports-imports), advertising, marketing strategy, materials management, consumers' behavior, market development and research.
- **Finanacial Management:** Includes all the aspects relating to finances, investments, financing decisions, portfolio management, project management, working capital management, international financial management, etc.
- **Production Management:** Takes care of Production methodology, costing, operations research and quality control etc.
- **Personnel Management:** Deals with the most complicated aspect i.e. management. It looks after the areas of Human Resource Development (HRD), Recruitment, Training, Management-Union Relations, Labor and Personnel Policies, Organization behavior, Management of Change and General Administration.